

The Blockchain of the Future

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

The speaker will present the concept of Blockchain Technology and Smart Contracts with emphasis on a real case example – OpenLedger ApS. The presentation will also emphasise on how individuals can use crowdfunding solutions in order to create their own tokens from scratch, and their own crowdfunding campaign. The real case example is given by the services offered by OpenLedger and their applicability in the process of token creation

2. Aim

To present the applicabilities and advantages of using Blockchain Technology gained by OpenLedger ApS and future partners such as: •Better performance •Removal of intermediaries •Faster transactions •Transparency and immutability (changes are viewable by all parties and can't be deleted) •Lower transaction costs •Durability, reliability and longevity (near impossible loss of data) •User empowerment

3. Material and Methods

The materials and examples used in this presentation will be based on OpenLedger's products and services with emphasis on BAAS (Blockchain as a service) and the services provided.

4. Results

The results are reflected in the success that OpenLedger has had so far and in their supported crowdfunding campaigns such as Crypviser, Centz and Karma plus the nearly foreseen projects such as OCASH, Getgame and eDev.

5. Conclusions

Knowledge transfer and transparency is of utmost importance. Therefore, OpenLedger is planning on providing and developing blockchain solutions together with their current and future partners.

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6. Key Words

Blockchain technology; Crypto-currency; Decentralised Exchange; OpenLedger; Smart Contracts; Crowdfunding; ITO/ICO;

Author biography

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